

Services and tools for Australian marine data discovery

The Marine Research Data Cloud aims to create a world-leading marine biological data advantage by improving workflows between major national research programs, major institutions, and major international programs.

A national service for the annotation of underwater imagery from Baited Remote Underwater Video (BRUV) will be developed.

Start date

2 January 2018

Expected completion date

2 January 2019

Investment by ARDC

\$600,000

Co-investment partners

[University of Tasmania](#)

[Atlas of Living Australia \(ALA\)](#)

[Australian Antarctic Division \(AAD\)](#)

[Geoscience Australia \(GA\)](#)

[Australian Research Data Commons \(ARDC\)](#)

[Australian Institute of Marine Science \(AIMS\)](#)

[Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network \(TERN\)](#)

[CSIRO Oceans & Atmosphere](#)

[UWA \(School of Biological Sciences\)](#)

[Greybits Engineering](#)

[Sydney Institute of Marine Science](#)

[Australian Coastal Ecosystems Facility \(ACEF\)](#)

[US-IOOS Animal Tracking Network](#)

[Integrated Marine observing System \(IMOS\)](#)

Lead node

UNIVERSITY of
TASMANIA

2. Annotation of underwater imagery

Develop a national service for annotation of underwater imagery from Baited Remote Underwater Video (BRUV).

4. Develop significant national collections

Transfer important data collections held by the Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network, Australian Coastal Ecosystems Facility (TERN ACEF facility) to the Australian Ocean Data Network (AODN), to ensure continued access. Publish near real-time surface wave data around Australia, and establish a national wave archive from 1974 to the present. Identify key turtle dataset collections and progress towards the development of a metadata catalogue of collections.

1. Workflows

Redefine workflow to significantly improve upload and accountability of uploading data to Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS), including an automated system to load all OBIS Australia data holdings into the Atlas of Living Australia (ALA). Previously unavailable biological data, including around 40 datasets managed by the Australian Antarctic Division, will be uploaded directly to OBIS International.

3. International collaboration

Progress International biologging collaboration, with a focus on exchange formats.

5. Institutional linkages

Advance AODN access to institutional repositories via institutional linkages, which is a big step towards the vision of a distributed network of online marine resources. Upgrade the existing infrastructure of each organisation and develop the AODN Portal to make use of existing web services and publish new dataset collections into the AODN Portal.

Core features

Annotation of underwater imagery

a national service for annotation of underwater imagery from Baited Remote Underwater Video (BRUV)

National collections

Access to significant national collections

International repositories

AODN access to institutional repositories

Who is this project for?

Marine researchers and those who require access to marine datasets.

What does this project enable?

Improved access to key datasets; a national service for annotation of underwater imagery from Baited Remote Underwater Video (BRUV). Standardisation of tools and workflow to enable researchers to easily upload imagery, have it catalogued, use and store annotations in a standardised repository.

Handy resources

Access the [AODN portal](#)
Visit the [Australian OBIS node](#)

<p>Australian Government Department of the Environment and Energy Australian Antarctic Division</p> <p>Australian Antarctic Division (AAD)</p> <p>VISIT</p>		
<p>Australian Institute of Marine Science</p> <p>Australian Institute of Marine Science (AIMS)</p> <p>VISIT</p>		
<p>THE UNIVERSITY OF WESTERN AUSTRALIA</p> <p>UWA (School of Biological Sciences)</p> <p>VISIT</p>		
<p>Australian Coastal Ecosystems Facility (ACEF)</p> <p>VISIT</p>		
<p>Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS)</p> <p>VISIT</p>		

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